

Entrepreneurship Training, Entrepreneurial Management, and Product Competitiveness: An Empirical Study of Small and Medium Micro Enterprises

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of Entrepreneurship Training through Entrepreneurial Management on Product Competitiveness in MSMEs. The approach used in this study is Quantitative explanatory and descriptive methods. The population of the study was MSMEs that had participated in entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial management training organized by the Sidenreng Rappang Regency Trade and Industry Office. The sample used was census sampling, all populations were made into the same sample of 40 respondents. Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire and analyzed with the help of the Structural Equation Modeling application using the Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) Version 4.00 method. Seen from the results of data processing through SEM-PLS. The results of the direct effect analysis showed that entrepreneurship training had a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial management and product competitiveness. While the indirect effect test showed that entrepreneurship training had a positive and significant effect on product competitiveness through entrepreneurial management as a mediating variable. Thus, all hypotheses proposed in this study can be accepted.

KEYWORDS: Entrepreneurship Training, Entrepreneurial Management, Product Competitiveness

A. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the largest cocoa and cashew commodities producing countries in the world. At the local level, Sidenreng Rappang Regency is one of the central areas producing these commodities. These potential places the cocoa and cashew processing business as a leading sector that plays a role in spurring regional economic growth and improving people's standard of living. However, the competitiveness of processed products in this area is still relatively low. Several contributing factors include inconsistent product quality, minimal innovation, and weak understanding of market needs. In this context, entrepreneurship training is an important intervention that is expected to be able to improve the competence of business actors, encourage innovation, and strengthen product competitiveness in a sustainable manner (Widhiyoga & Wijayati, 2022)

Various previous studies have emphasized that entrepreneurship training and entrepreneurial management have a positive effect on product competitiveness. Research Gielnik et al., (2019) shows that entrepreneurship training has a positive effect on entrepreneurial management through business income. Meanwhile, Siregar et al., (2024) concluded that entrepreneurial management has a positive and significant effect on product competitiveness. (Randos, 2024) stated that entrepreneurship training and entrepreneurial management have a positive and significant effect on business competitiveness. By combining this literature, it can be concluded that this study obtains theoretical support from various previous studies, thus strengthening the argument that entrepreneurial management can be a mediating variable that bridges the influence of entrepreneurship training on product competitiveness.

By considering the description in the background, the formulation of the problem in this study can be formulated as follows: (1) what is the impact of entrepreneurship training on product competitiveness in MSMEs, (2) what is the impact of entrepreneurship training on entrepreneurial management in MSMEs, (3) what is the impact of entrepreneurial management on product competitiveness in MSMEs, (4) what is the impact or influence of entrepreneurship training on product competitiveness through entrepreneurial management in MSMEs.

The main objective of this study is to analyze the extent to which entrepreneurship training and entrepreneurial management affect product competitiveness in MSMEs. This study can provide an overview of how effective entrepreneurship training and entrepreneurial management are in helping business actors improve the competitiveness of MSME products. This is the background

for researchers to raise this topic to find out how entrepreneurship training and entrepreneurial management affect product competitiveness in MSMEs.

B. LITERATUR REVIEW

1. Entrepreneurship

The definition of entrepreneurship has been described by various experts through their respective contributions. Robbins and Coulter in their research (Yulia et al., 2022) stated that entrepreneurship is a process of starting a new business that usually arises as a response to an opportunity. Meanwhile, Rakib et al., (2024) entrepreneurship refers to all aspects involved in becoming an entrepreneur. The term entrepreneur provides a description of the nature of courage referring to business activities, both commercial and non-commercial. Entrepreneurship reflects the mental attitude, enthusiasm, and ability to produce new things that are useful, both for oneself and others. Research by Isma, Rakib, and Halim (2022) also revealed that entrepreneurship training is an effective solution to develop entrepreneurial character, such as independence, creativity, and innovation. This character plays an important role in supporting individuals to face business challenges and create strategies that increase product competitiveness. Thus, entrepreneurship training not only equips individuals with practical skills but also forms a mindset and character that supports sustainable business success (Isma et al., 2022).

2. Entrepreneurship Training

Entrepreneurship training is a structured learning process that aims to improve the ability of individuals or groups to develop and manage businesses independently, creatively, and innovatively (Aransyah et al., 2023). In addition, it explains that entrepreneurship training is a learning process designed to equip individuals with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to become strong business actors, so that they are able to create new entrepreneurs who make real contributions to the progress of the nation. This training plays an important role in determining the effectiveness of the learning process, where the right method can facilitate an in-depth understanding of business planning, financial management, risk taking, and evaluation and development of service products according to market needs. Entrepreneurship training is an effort made through improving business skills possessed by entrepreneurs through improving knowledge, attitudes, and skills (Muhammad Rakib, 2017). In my research entitled "Entrepreneurship Training, Entrepreneurial Management, and Product Competitiveness: An Empirical Study of MSMEs in Sidenreng Rappang Regency" entrepreneurship training is the key to improving business skills and product competitiveness, so this study aims to determine how entrepreneurship training and entrepreneurial management can affect product competitiveness (M Rakib et al., 2020).

In the context of this study, indicators of training methods, facilities and infrastructure are important things in training and support the implementation of training for optimal learning. understanding of participants to measure the extent to which the training is successful in improving the competence and performance of participants in running the participant's business. the ability to deliver material is also an important indicator to ensure that the information and skills delivered can be taken and implemented by participants, so that they are able to achieve business success and increase business competitiveness in the market. Training methods are a crucial component in efforts to increase the independence of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). In addition to training methods, facilities and infrastructure also play an important role in the success of entrepreneurship training programs (Sari & Kusumawati, 2022). Adequate facilities such as comfortable training rooms, information technology equipment, relevant learning materials, and access to other supporting resources greatly support the learning process. The training provided not only improves the technical skills of participants but also affects the business performance of the business after training. The quality of material delivery greatly determines the extent to which participants can understand and apply the knowledge provided. Competent presenters who are able to deliver material clearly and interestingly will increase participant engagement and facilitate a more effective learning process (Crane et al., 2019).

3. Entrepreneurial Management

Drucker defines entrepreneurial management as a process involving an individual's ability to identify opportunities, manage resources, and make strategic decisions to create added value in a business. In the context of micro, small, and medium enterprises or abbreviated (MSMEs), entrepreneurial management has a very important role in maintaining business continuity (Drucker, 2017). Good entrepreneurial management can have a positive impact on the sustainability of MSMEs. This shows that entrepreneurial

management is not only a theory, but also has practical benefits for small business actors. The core of this management includes adjusting business strategies to suit market needs and developing human resource capabilities within the business. One very important aspect in entrepreneurial management is opportunity identification. Opportunity identification refers to the entrepreneur's ability to recognize, analyze, and utilize potential market opportunities for business development (Jarvis, 2016). Entrepreneurial management not only includes the ability to identify opportunities, but also other important aspects, namely operational cost efficiency. Operational cost efficiency is key to increasing the independence of MSMEs, because it can reduce expenses and increase profit margins. In the context of entrepreneurial management, important indicators such as business planning, creativity, opportunity identification, and operational efficiency are key factors in the success of this study (Triwahyono et al., 2023).

4. Product Competitiveness

Product competitiveness is the ability of a product to compete in the market by offering more value than competitors, both in terms of quality, price, innovation, and uniqueness. This concept originally emerged from Ricardo's theory of comparative advantage in the 18th century and has continued to develop into a major factor in meeting global market needs (Siddiqui, 2018). Not only limited to MSMEs, product competitiveness in general is influenced by several factors, including product quality, innovation and adaptation to consumer needs. Product competitiveness at the micro level, as explained by classical microeconomic theory, is related to the company's ability to create added value and optimize profits. Therefore, the ability to improve product quality, and innovate in creating uniqueness are important indicators of product competitiveness. Further understanding of competitiveness has also been put forward by several previous studies. Product quality and product innovation are two main factors that determine competitive advantage. Product quality includes durability, function, and suitability of the product to consumer needs. On the other hand, product innovation plays a role in creating added value through design, features, or creative approaches that differentiate products from competitors. Product competitiveness is not only determined by quality and innovation, but also consumer satisfaction as an indicator of success in maintaining market share (Sarkar et al., 2024). Consumer satisfaction is the result of a positive experience obtained by consumers when using a product or service, which is influenced by product quality, competitive prices, and the services provided (Mahsyar & Surapati, 2020).

C. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a Quantitative Explanatory model with a conclusive design using a descriptive method. According to (Creswell, 2017) quantitative explanatory research is explaining or predicting the relationship between variables by testing previously formulated theories or hypotheses. Quantitative Explanatory was chosen because this study aims to analyze and explain the influence between entrepreneurial training variables, entrepreneurial management mediation variables and product competitiveness variables on MSMEs. This research was conducted precisely the MSMEs spread across 11 sub-districts in Sidenreng Rappang Regency who had participated in MSME training held by the Department of Industry and Trade in collaboration with the Ganggawa Institute. This research lasted for two months until the data processing process and analyzed the results obtained at the research location. The population of this study was all business actors who had participated in entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial management training organized by the Sidenreng Rappang Regency Trade and Industry Office in collaboration with the Ganggawa Institute in 2024, totaling 40 people. The sampling technique used the census sampling technique. With the census sampling technique, the number of samples used as respondents was 40 people who had participated in entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial management training at MSMEs in Sidenreng Rappang Regency. Data collection techniques are carried out in two stages, namely observation and questionnaires. Observation to observe and collect accurate, valid data and obtain relevant and useful conclusions for researchers. Questionnaires to measure the influence of entrepreneurial training variables and entrepreneurial management on product competitiveness. Data are collected through direct questionnaires and online surveys. The data analysis technique used statistical software analysis Structural Equation Modeling method Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS), and path analysis was conducted to test the hypothesis and see the effect of independent variables (entrepreneurship training) mediation variables (entrepreneurship management) on dependent variables (product competitiveness). This analysis aims to analyze the effect of entrepreneurship training on product competitiveness through entrepreneurship management.

D. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

1. Respondent Characteristics

The characteristics of the 40 respondents in this study showed that the majority were women, with a total of 30 people or around 75% of the total respondents, while male respondents only numbered 10 people or around 25%. The dominance of female respondents shows that women have a higher interest and participation in developing entrepreneurship. The majority of respondents are from Panca Lautang with a percentage of 47.5%. These results indicate that participants from Panca Lautang are the main center of the MSME industry in Sidenreng Rappang Regency. The majority of respondents in the cashew business sector numbered 26 people or around 65%, while chocolate numbered 14 or around 35%. These results indicate that this is due to factors such as the availability of raw materials, market demand, and support from the government and business community in the area.

2. Entrepreneurship Training Description

Entrepreneurship training is a learning process designed to improve the insight, skills, and attitudes of business actors in creating economic independence. This training includes effective training methods, facilities and infrastructure, understanding of materials and the quality of training facilitators. The average value of the entrepreneurship training variable indicator is 3.73, which indicates that the training has been carried out well, where the methods used are easy to understand, the facilities provided are adequate, and the materials presented are able to improve the understanding and competence of participants. This achievement indicates that the training has a positive impact on the readiness of participants to develop businesses independently and competitively.

3. Entrepreneurial Management Description

Entrepreneurial management is a process that involves planning, organizing, directing, and controlling all available resources to achieve business goals in an effective and efficient manner. Entrepreneurial management includes the ability to design a business, be creative, take advantage of opportunities, and be able to manage operations. The average value of the variable indicator is 3.88, which indicates that training participants have a good understanding and application of entrepreneurial management. The four indicators show consistency in implementing important aspects of business management, from the planning stage, developing ideas, to implementing efficient operations. These results reflect that the training program has succeeded in equipping participants with adequate managerial skills to support the success of the participants' businesses.

4. Product Competitiveness Description

Product competitiveness is the ability of a product to compete with other products in meeting consumer needs, both in terms of quality, price, innovation, and product uniqueness. In this study, the indicators used to measure product competitiveness include product quality, product innovation, and consumer satisfaction. The average value of the product competitiveness variable indicator of 4.52 indicates that the products produced by training participants have very good competitiveness in the market. The high score indicates that participants have a strong understanding of the importance of maintaining quality, creating innovation, and meeting consumer expectations, which overall are advantages in maintaining the existence of their business.

5. Hypothesis Testing

The inferential analysis method used in this study is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach, which includes two main stages, namely outer model and inner model measurements. Data processing in this study was carried out with the help of SmartPLS software version 4.00. In this model, several variable abbreviations are used to facilitate visualization. ET stands for Entrepreneurship Training, which is measured through four main indicators, namely training methods, facilities and infrastructure, understanding of training participants, and ability to deliver material. EM stands for Entrepreneur Management which includes indicators of business planning, creativity, opportunity identification, and operational efficiency. While PC stands for Product Competitiveness, which is formed from three indicators, namely product quality, product innovation, and consumer satisfaction. The results of testing the relationship path between these variables are shown in the figure below:

Figure 5.1 Hypothesis Testing Results.

Figure 1. Research Model Results

a. Construct Validity

Based on the test using SmartPLS on the outer model, it can be seen that the value of each indicator or outer loading value shows a number above 0.7. In addition, referring to the AVE value listed in the table, all variables show a score of more than 0.5. This finding indicates that each variable has met the criteria for adequate discriminant validity. Thus, all indicators used in this study can be declared valid because they have met the requirements for convergent validity and are worthy of further analysis in the next stage.

Table 5.1 Results of Loading Factor and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Indicator	Outer Loading Value	AVE	Information
Entrepreneurship Training			
ET1	0.741	0.605	Valid
ET2	0.819		Valid
ET3	0.849		Valid
ET 4	0.781		Valid
ET5	0.742		Valid
ET6	0.716		Valid
ET7	0.793		Valid
ET8	0.705		Valid
ET9	0.800		Valid
ET10	0.770		Valid
ET11	0.816		Valid
ET12	0.766		Valid
ET13	0.798		Valid
Entrepreneur Management			
EM1	0.816	0.645	Valid
EM2	0.755		Valid

EM3	0.800	Valid
EM4	0.764	Valid
EM5	0.773	Valid
EM6	0.826	Valid
EM7	0.821	Valid
EM8	0.781	Valid
EM9	0.846	Valid
EM10	0.830	Valid
EM11	0.865	Valid
EM12	0.747	Valid
Product Competitiveness		
PC1	0.804	Valid
PC2	0.797	Valid
PC3	0.772	Valid
PC4	0.741	Valid
PC5	0.828	0.621
PC6	0.817	Valid
PC7	0.729	Valid
PC8	0.793	Valid
PC9	0.804	Valid

Source: Data Processing Results (2025)

To evaluate the discriminant validity in this study, the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) approach was used. The criteria used refer to the maximum limit of 0.9 as suggested by (Sarstedt et al., 2021).

Table 5.2 Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio Results

Variables	Product Competitiveness	Entrepreneur Management
Product Competitiveness		
Entrepreneur Management	0.812	
Entrepreneurship Training	0.832	0.788

Source: Data Processing Results (2025)

Based on the calculation of HTMT values shown in the previous table, all variables in the research model show scores below 0.9. This indicates that each construct has met the requirements of discriminant validity and can be declared valid.

b. Reliability Composite

From the results of the composite reliability calculation of the three constructs in this research model, all values show numbers above 0.7. Thus, it can be concluded that all constructs are reliable and consistent in representing the concepts being measured.

Table 5.3 Composite Reliability Results

Variables	Composite reliability
Product Competitiveness	0.928
Entrepreneur Management	0.952
Entrepreneurship Training	0.947

Source: Data Processing Results, 2025.

c. Direct Effects & Indirect Effects

Hypothesis testing is carried out by paying attention to T-statistics values of more than 1.96 or p-values that are smaller than the significance level (<0.05) indicating that a relationship exists. between variables is significant. Indirect influence is carried out if the independent variable influences the dependent variable through the mediating role of other variables. The results of the mediation test are calculated using the Variance Accounted For (VAF) approach, to determine whether the mediation that occurs is partial or full. The results of the research hypothesis evaluation can be seen in the following table:

Table 5.4 Direct Effect & Indirect Effect

Variables	Original sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
X > Y	0.479	0.509	0.122	3.938	0.000
X > Z	0.759	0.764	0.072	10,499	0.000
Z > Y	0.412	0.382	0.135	3.055	0.002
X > Z > Y	0.313	0.291	0.107	2.925	0.003

Source: Data Processing Results (2025)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the evaluation of the hypothesis directly and indirectly, the acceptance of the hypothesis where the p-values are below 0.05 and the T-statistics are above 1.96. The conclusion is that these four hypotheses are declared accepted according to their acceptance standards. Based on the data listed above, it can be concluded that the findings of this study related to the evaluation of the hypothesis are obtained as follows:

1. Entrepreneurship training has a positive and significant impact on product competitiveness.
2. Entrepreneurship training has a positive and significant impact on entrepreneurial management.
3. Entrepreneurial management has a positive and significant influence on product competitiveness.
4. Entrepreneurship training has a positive and significant impact on product competitiveness through entrepreneurial management.

Discussion

The Influence of Entrepreneurship Training on Product Competitiveness

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, it was obtained that the entrepreneurship training variable had a positive and significant effect on product competitiveness, as evidenced by the P-Value of 0.000 and the T-Statistic of 3.720 which exceeded the t-table of 1.96. In addition, the original sample value of 0.444 showed that every increase in the implementation of entrepreneurship training would be followed by an increase in product competitiveness. This indicates that the better the training method, availability of facilities and infrastructure, understanding of training participants, and the ability to deliver material by instructors, the higher the product quality, innovation, and consumer satisfaction produced by business actors. Thus, it can be concluded that entrepreneurship training makes a significant contribution to increasing product competitiveness in MSMEs. In this study, it is strengthened by the Resource-Based View (RBV) approach developed by Barney in Lubis, (2022) which highlights the importance of strengthening internal resources such as skills and knowledge in order to achieve competitive advantage. Through entrepreneurship training, business actors gain core competencies in creating and maintaining superior products in terms of quality and innovation, thereby encouraging increased product competitiveness in the market. Entrepreneurship training contributes greatly to strengthening product competitiveness starting from creating jobs, productivity and participants are able to improve their skills which ultimately have an impact on participants' ability to produce superior products and compete in the market (Muhammad Rakib, 2022). Entrepreneurship training indicators, training methods, facilities and infrastructure, participant understanding and material delivery capabilities have a positive role in creating product competitiveness. This is evidenced by the validity of all statements presented through the questionnaire. These results indicate that entrepreneurship training has a positive and significant effect on product competitiveness. This finding indicates that the more effective the implementation of entrepreneurship training, both in terms of methods, materials, and facilities provided, the higher the ability of business actors to create superior and competitive products. These results are in line with previous studies such as those conducted by Goit & Barus,

(2024), Randos (2024) Randos, (2024) and Li et al., (2023) which directly support the first hypothesis, namely that entrepreneurship training has a positive and significant effect on product competitiveness.

The Influence of Entrepreneurship Training on Entrepreneurial Management

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, it is known that Entrepreneurship Training has a positive and significant effect on Entrepreneurial Management as indicated by the P-Value of 0.000 and T-Statistics of 9.991, much greater than the t-table of 1.96. The Original Sample Value of 0.779 indicates that the better the implementation of entrepreneurship training which includes training methods, availability of facilities and infrastructure, level of participant understanding, and ability to deliver material, the better the quality of entrepreneurial management of business actors. This increase can be seen from the increasingly good business planning, creativity, ability to identify opportunities, and operational efficiency possessed by training participants. Thus, entrepreneurship training has been proven to provide a strong contribution to improving entrepreneurial management in MSMEs in Sidenreng Rappang Regency. In this study, it is reinforced by the Human Capital Theory developed by Becker in Marginson, (2019) which emphasizes that training is a form of investment in improving the quality of human resources. Entrepreneurship training provides a real contribution to improving the managerial competence of business actors, such as business planning, operational efficiency, and creativity, which are important aspects in effective entrepreneurial management.

This is reinforced by Muhammad Rakib, (2018) who stated that entrepreneurship training is important in creating effective entrepreneurial management, because training can shape the mindset, attitudes, and managerial skills needed to run a business sustainably and professionally. Training that is systematically designed with the right method supported by adequate facilities and professional delivery of materials, is able to improve participants' understanding and skills in running a business. These results support the importance of the sustainability of entrepreneurship training programs as one strategy in strengthening entrepreneurial management. These findings prove that entrepreneurship training has a positive and significant influence on entrepreneurial management. These results indicate that effective training not only improves business understanding and skills, but also strengthens managerial aspects such as business planning, creativity, opportunity identification, and operational efficiency of business actors. The findings are supported by several previous studies such as Gielnik et al., (2019) and (Ni'mah et al., 2021) which prove that entrepreneurship training has a positive influence on entrepreneurial management.

The Influence of Entrepreneurial Management on Product Competitiveness

Based on the results of the analysis of the hypothesis testing of the entrepreneurial management variable (Z) it is proven to have a positive and significant influence on product competitiveness (Y). which is indicated by the P-Values value of 0.001 and the T-Statistics value of 3.387. In addition, the original sample value of 0.464 indicates that every increase in the quality of entrepreneurial management will be followed by an increase in business competitiveness. This indicates that the more optimal the business management in terms of planning, creativity, opportunity identification, and efficiency, the higher the ability of business actors to create superior and competitive products. It can be concluded that entrepreneurial management makes a significant contribution to increasing product competitiveness in MSMEs. This study explains the Dynamic Capability Theory developed by Teece, (2018) emphasizing the importance of dynamic capabilities in creating and maintaining competitive advantage. In the context of this hypothesis, entrepreneurial management reflects the adaptive and innovative capabilities of business actors in responding to market dynamics, which ultimately has an impact on increasing product competitiveness. These results indicate that the better the implementation of entrepreneurial management, the higher the competitiveness of the products produced. Business actors who are able to prepare mature business plans, apply creativity in business management, identify market opportunities carefully, and run business operations efficiently, will work better to produce quality, innovative products, and adapt to consumer needs and expectations. These results indicate that entrepreneurial management has a positive and significant effect on product competitiveness. This finding shows that the better the ability of entrepreneurs to plan, manage, and develop their business, the higher the competitiveness of the products produced. These results are reinforced by several previous studies Siregar et al., (2024), Yustian et al., (2021) and Rahmawati et al., (2022) directly support the third hypothesis, namely that entrepreneurial management has a positive and significant effect on product competitiveness.

The Influence of Entrepreneurship Training on Product Competitiveness through Entrepreneurial Management

The results of the indirect effect hypothesis test show that the entrepreneurship training variable has a positive and significant effect on product competitiveness through entrepreneurial management as a mediating variable. This is indicated by the

P-Values of 0.001 which is smaller than 0.05 and the T-table value of 3.180 which exceeds the threshold of 1.96. In addition, the sample value of 0.361 indicates that the indirect effect of entrepreneurship training on product competitiveness through entrepreneurial management has a fairly strong relationship strength. Entrepreneurship training not only has a direct impact on product competitiveness, but also has a significant indirect impact through improving entrepreneurial management. In other words, the more effective the entrepreneurship training received by entrepreneurs, both in terms of training methods, facilities, understanding of materials, and practical experience provided, the better the business management that is run. This ultimately encourages increased product competitiveness, both in terms of quality, innovation, and product excellence in the market. These results indicate that entrepreneurial management plays an important role as a mediating variable in strengthening the influence of entrepreneurial training on product competitiveness. In other words, without strengthening the quality of entrepreneurial management, the training provided may not be fully able to increase product competitiveness optimally. Therefore, it can be concluded that the strategy for increasing product competitiveness in MSMEs needs to pay attention to the role of entrepreneurial training that is strategically designed and integrated with the development of entrepreneurial management capabilities. Based on the calculation results of the Variance Accounted For (VAF) value, a value of 39.5% was obtained. This value is in the range of 20% to 80%, which according to Ghazali in the study (Indarti, 2021) shows that the influence of entrepreneurship training variables on product competitiveness through entrepreneurial management is partial (partial mediation). It can be concluded that entrepreneurial management is able to be a partial mediating variable in this relationship. This study illustrates that entrepreneurship training has a positive and significant influence on product competitiveness through entrepreneurial management as a mediating variable. Although there has been no previous research that directly evaluates the indirect relationship between entrepreneurship training and product competitiveness through entrepreneurial management, this hypothesis is indirectly supported by several previous research results. Entrepreneurship training has a positive influence on product competitiveness (Randos, 2024); Goit & Barus, (2024); (Li et al., 2023).

By combining these findings, it can be concluded that although indirectly, the fourth hypothesis in this study obtains theoretical support from various previous studies, thus strengthening the argument that entrepreneurial management can be a mediating variable that bridges the influence of entrepreneurial training on product competitiveness.

E. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results obtained in the study on entrepreneurship training, entrepreneurial management, product competitiveness: an empirical study of MSMEs. From the analysis, it can be concluded as follows Entrepreneurship training has a direct and significant influence on product competitiveness in MSMEs. Entrepreneurship training has a direct and significant influence on entrepreneurial management in MSMEs. Entrepreneurial management has a direct and significant influence on product competitiveness in MSMEs. Entrepreneurship training has an indirect and significant influence on product competitiveness through entrepreneurial management in MSMEs in Sidenreng Rappang Regency.

Based on the results of the research and discussion that has been done, the researcher provides several suggestions, namely: It is expected that business actors who participate in entrepreneurship training can be more active in understanding and implementing the material provided. The related agencies that organize the training, the Cooperative and SME Service of Sidenreng Rappang Regency and the accompanying institution Ganggawa Institute, are expected to continue to improve the quality of entrepreneurship training, both in terms of methods, materials, and facilities provided. This study still has limitations, especially in the scope of the object which only covers cashew and chocolate processing centers in Sidenreng Rappang Regency. Therefore, further researchers are expected to be able to expand the scope of the area or add other variables such as entrepreneurship training, business performance, and test similar models in different business sectors to obtain more comprehensive and generalizable results.

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